

INTEGRATING SYSTEMS THINKING LEARNING APPROACH: EFFECTS ON LEARNERS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND SELF-EFFICACY IN SCIENCE

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ABSTRACT

Teachers in 21st century is challenged to implement research-based strategies that can improve the academic achievements. The researcher only conducted a study on self-efficacy and academic performance among Grade 7 learners in Science at Batangan Integrated School, using the Systems Thinking Learning Approach. Specifically, it aimed to determine the level of learners' academic achievement in Science when exposed to STLA and those exposed to non-STLA; describe the self-efficacy of learners toward Science when exposed to the STLA and non-STLA; find out if there is a significant difference in the learners' academic achievement in Science when exposed to the STLA from those in non-STLA; ascertain if there is a significant difference in the level of self-efficacy of learners when exposed to the STLA from those in non-STLA. Quasi-experimental research involved both the STLA and non-STLA groups. The instruments used included a teacher-made questionnaire and a non-academic assessment. Both questionnaires were field-tested for reliability and content validation. The study's findings showed that learners exposed to an STLA achieved a mean score with above-average results in science, while the non-STLA group's scores were only in the average range. Learners exposed to STLA showed high self-efficacy in perceived control, competence, persistence, and self-regulated learning. In contrast, those in the non-STLA group showed moderately positive. Significant differences were also observed in academic achievement and self-efficacy between the two groups. The results indicate that STLA is an effective strategy for enhancing the academic performance and self-efficacy of learners.

Keywords: *(self-efficacy, academic achievement, systems thinking learning approach)*

INTRODUCTION

To succeed in today's world, learners require a Science education that equips them with the knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary for comprehending the natural world, resolving complex problems, and making informed decisions in everyday life. It goes beyond just gaining knowledge, fostering important qualities such as creativity, curiosity, and critical thinking, which are vital for both personal growth and societal progress.

In line with its goal to promote science education across the country, the Department of Education introduced the MATATAG Curriculum in 2023. This curriculum aims to equip learners to face future challenges by incorporating 21st-century skills and preparing them to succeed in both local and global markets. The MATATAG Curriculum envisions lifelong, peace-minded Filipino learners who are well-rounded and ready for the future, embodying the core values of *Maka-Diyos, Makatao, Makakalikasan, and Makabansa* (Department of Education, 2023).

Despite these efforts, challenges in learner performance persist at international, national, and local levels, despite ongoing reforms in the education sector and other intervention programs. According to the 2022 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), Filipino learners were reported to still perform substantially below the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) average, especially in science. In an alarming statistic, 16 percent of Filipino learners achieved a level 2 proficiency in science and reading, a level deemed the minimum required to contribute efficiently to society today. As seen in these results, there is a continued lack of foundational learning, underscoring the need to implement more effective and innovative teaching methods that can enhance scientific literacy and increase the depth of knowledge among students (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2023).

This challenge is also reflected in the academic performance data from Batangan Integrated School at the local level. CMSS (Curriculum Management Support System) results for Science 7 showed that 31.82% of learners received satisfactory scores (between 80 and 84), while 27.27% achieved excellent scores (between 90 and 100) among 110 learners. However, 20 percent of the learners scored below satisfactory, with scores between 75 and 79, struggling to grasp basic scientific concepts. Moreover, 20.91% of learners scored between 85 and 89, indicating satisfactory performance rather than exceptional achievement. These results reveal both strengths and areas that still need improvement. (Batangan Integrated School, 2024).

These performance disparities underscore the need to adopt inclusive and adaptive teaching strategies that cater to the diverse needs of learners. One promising pedagogy is the systems thinking learning approach, which encourages learners to view scientific concepts as parts of a larger whole. Indeed, the effects of systems thinking in secondary

education have not been extensively studied. According to Bozkurt (2023), systems thinking is a crucial critical thinking skill that should be incorporated into science education. Since it involves understanding causal relationships between system components and making connections between scientific knowledge and real-world issues, adopting a systems thinking approach can boost learners' confidence in solving problems. This increased confidence improves their self-efficacy, motivating them to dedicate more effort and time to learning science and helping them persist through academic challenges.

Learners who have high academic self-efficacy tend to adopt and practice effective cognitive and metacognitive learning processes, and will also show persistence when coping with academic demands, ultimately achieving better academic outcomes. The beliefs about self-efficacy influence the work of learners, with more planning, monitoring, and effort regulation strategies being common among learners with high self-efficacy (Artino, 2012).

In this study, the researcher investigated impact of the STLA on Grade 7 Science learners' academic achievement and self-efficacy. The results can be of use to the teachers and school leaders in creating new and improved teaching methods that can contribute to efforts to improve learners' global competitiveness and performance in international assessments such as PISA.

Research Questions

This study aimed to investigate the effects of the Systems thinking learning approach on learners' academic achievement and self-efficacy in Grade 7 Science of Batangan Integrated School, Batangan, Valencia City, Bukidnon.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of learners' academic achievement in science when exposed to Systems thinking learning approach, and those exposed to non-Systems thinking learning approach, in terms of:
 - a. pre-test; and
 - b. post-test?
2. What is the level of self-efficacy of learners toward science learning when exposed to the Systems thinking approach and non-Systems thinking learning approach, in terms of:
 - a. perceived control;
 - b. competence;
 - c. persistence; and
 - d. self-regulated learning?
3. Is there a significant difference in learners' academic achievement in science when exposed to a Systems thinking learning approach compared to those in a non-Systems thinking learning approach?

4. Is there a significant difference in the level of self-efficacy of learners when exposed to the Systems thinking learning approach from those in a non-Systems thinking learning approach, in terms of:
- a. perceived control;
 - b. competence;
 - c. persistence; and
 - d. self-regulated learning?

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the research design, locale of the study, respondents of the study, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and statistical analysis used.

Research Design

A quasi-experimental research design was used to assess learners' academic achievement and self-efficacy in science. The participants consisted of two diverse sections of grade 7 students officially enrolled during the fourth grading period of school year 2024-2025 at Batangan Integrated School. This study involved two intact classes; one class implemented the Systems thinking learning approach (experimental group), while the other used the non-Systems thinking learning approach (control group).

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at Batangan Integrated School, School ID No. 501120, located at Purok 10, Batangan, Valencia City, Bukidnon. The school offers a comprehensive curriculum that includes the Basic Education Curriculum, the Special Science Program for elementary learners, and the Junior High School Program. Additionally, it has a Senior High School program featuring the Academic strand of Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) and Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS). It aims to promote intellectual and personal growth, aligning with the community's educational framework. The education is of high quality, delivered in a supportive and inclusive learning environment where everyone can thrive. The school boasts an ideal setting that reflects its commitment to academic excellence and holistic development.

Participants of the Study

The study participants were two (2) diverse sections of grade-7 learners officially enrolled in Batangan Integrated School during the fourth grading period, school year 2024-2025. One section of 36 students, utilized the systems thinking learning approach (experimental group). The experimental group was composed of heterogeneous learners aged 12 to 15. In contrast, the other section, comprising 36 learners, utilized the non-systems thinking learning approach (control group).

Research Instruments

The study employed both academic and non-academic assessments.

A. Academic Assessment

An achievement test was used to measure the learners' academic achievement. The researcher initially developed one hundred (100) multiple-choice items covering Grade 7 Science for Quarter 4, specifically focusing on System Models, Earthquakes, and The Sun's Influence on Earth. A Table of Specifications (TOS) was prepared to verify that the content and topics aligned with Bloom's revised taxonomy levels. To ensure the validity of the test items, the materials were reviewed by local experts. Specifically, three science experts evaluated the materials: two from Central Mindanao University and one from Batangan Integrated School. After the expert validation, the questionnaire was administered to one (1) section of Grade 8 learners at Batangan Integrated School to assess its reliability. It yielded a Cronbach's alpha of .90; based on the results, the test was refined to eighty (80) items. The final questionnaire was then given to the Grade 7 learners who participated in the study.

The interpretation of learners' academic achievement was based on a proficiency scale that was adapted from the study "Concrete-Pictorial-Abstract Approach on Students' Attitude and Performance in Mathematics" (Salingay & Tan, 2018). This scale categorizes learner scores into levels of proficiency according to percentage ranges.

The overall mean score was interpreted using the data presented below.

Raw score	Range	Level of Proficiency	Qualitative Interpretation
65 – 80	81%-100%	Exemplary	Very High Performance
49 – 64	61%-80%	Above Average	High Performance
33 – 48	41%-60%	Average	Moderate Performance
17 – 32	21%-40%	Below Average	Low Performance
1 – 16	1%-20%	Deficient	Very Low Performance

B. Non-academic Assessment

The Learner's Survey Questionnaire on Self-Efficacy (Dullas, 2018) was used to measure learners' self-efficacy. It consists of fifty-six (56) questions across four (4) self-efficacy-related subscales: perceived control with 11 items, competence with 14 items, persistence with 11 items, and self-regulated learning with 20 items. Additionally, a five (5) point Likert scale was used to analyze the learners' self-efficacy. Below is the scale used for data interpretation. The material has a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.87.

Rating	Scale	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
5	4.51-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Self-Efficacy
4	3.51-4.50	Agree	High Self-Efficacy
3	2.51-3.50	Undecided	Moderate Self-Efficacy

2	1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low Self-Efficacy
1	1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Self-Efficacy

Data Gathering Procedure

Before conducting the study, approval was obtained from the IERC to ensure compliance with research guidelines. A request for approval was sent to the School Division Superintendent of the Valencia Division. A formal letter was also sent to the Principal of Batangan Integrated School, seeking permission to conduct the study among Grade 7 learners enrolled in the Fourth Quarter of SY 2024-2025. The experimental group experienced a six-step Systems Thinking learning process, while the control group was taught using the 7E learning method. In Quarter 4, the study included system models, earthquakes, and the Sun's influence on Earth. The researcher selected activities from various sources, including textbooks and online resources. Science experts reviewed the content of these learning activities. Before implementing the approach, the participants signed a consent letter that outlined the study's purpose and ensured confidentiality. A pre-test was given before the experimental period to assess the learners' prior academic achievement of the content. During the implementation, one section was exposed to the Systems Thinking Learning Approach, and one was exposed to the non-Systems Thinking Learning Approach. Then, after completing all the lessons, a post-test was given to both groups. The Learners' Survey Questionnaire on Self-Efficacy was also given to determine the learners' self-efficacy.

Implementation of the Systems Thinking Learning Approach for Learning Science

The utilization of the Systems Thinking Learning Approach in this study was guided by the 7E Learning Model (Elicit, Engage, Explore, Explain, Elaborate, Evaluate, and Extend). It was adapted from Goodman et al. (2015) "Six Steps to Thinking Systemically" and from The Systems Thinker and Edutopia's (2022) article, Teaching K-12 Students Systems Thinking. The integration of these frameworks aimed to foster an in-depth understanding of scientific concepts and their interconnections through student-centered, planned activities.

Elicit -Set the Stage:

In this phase, learners recalled their prior knowledge, and the framework of systems thinking was explained to them in simple terms and real-world scenarios. They started to understand that they needed to shift from linear thinking and view things in a more integrated way.

Engage - Specify the System:

In this phase, learners identified a real-world problem and, with the teacher, defined the system's boundaries and key components. They effectively described the system and pinpointed the main issue, which will be investigated by the end of the process.

Explore - Sketch the System:

In this phase, learners created system diagrams that include connection circles and a causal loop diagram to illustrate component interactions. They developed a working model that demonstrated the system's complexity and structure.

Explain- Spot Patterns:

During this phase, the learners analyzed their diagrams with the teacher's guidance to identify feedback loops, delays, and recurring patterns. They showed their understanding by explaining the system's behavior using these insights.

Elaborate - Solve and Demonstrate:

In this phase, learners proposed several potential solutions to the problem and forecasted the consequences of their interventions using a model or demonstration. They showed their ability to apply systems thinking to solve problems.

Evaluate- Summarize and Share:

In this phase, learners summarized their results through presentations, reflections, or creative projects. They were able to communicate what they learned and assess their development in systems thinking.

Extend- Summarize and Share:

In this phase, learners would apply systems thinking concepts to other topics or real-life experiences. They also demonstrated their ability to transfer and generalize their knowledge to a broader scope.

Implementation of the Non-Systems Thinking Learning Approach for Learning Science

For groups not engaged in a Systems thinking learning approach, they were taught using conventional learning methods. The MATATAG curriculum lesson plan and the 7 E's learning model were employed. Students worked with materials provided by the Department of Education (DepEd) and their performance tasks. These materials underwent validation by Science Master Teachers or Module Validators to ensure quality in the region. Assessment was conducted through activities, answer sheets, and performance tasks.

Elicit - Activated pre-existing knowledge of the learners by asking them a question based on their previous experiences and connecting it to the new lesson.

Engage - Got the minds of the learners entertained over the topic by posing them a lengthy thought-provoking question and also with an image that will interest them.

Explore - Introduced learners to a general practical experience that enabled them explore and uncover certain patterns or concepts themselves.

Explain - Provided the concept in an approachable way but also making learners discuss the idea and share their thoughts to help them to get a clear understanding of ideas and dispel some misconceptions.

Elaborate - Had learners apply the information learned in the Explain phase by solving problems and engaging in group activities to extend understanding.

Evaluate - Determined whether the concepts were mastered by the learners using oral questioning, written activities, and performance-based tasks.

Extend - Deepened learners' conceptual understanding by having them apply their knowledge to a new situation or real-life context.

Statistical Techniques

Descriptive statistics, including frequency values, means, percentages, and standard deviations, were used to assess learners' academic achievement and self-efficacy in Science, influenced by the integration of Systems Thinking and non-Systems Thinking learning approaches.

To determine if there were statistically significant differences in academic achievement between learners exposed to the Systems Thinking Learning Approach and those taught using a non-Systems Thinking approach, the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was applied to the post-test scores, with pre-test scores as covariates.

The ANCOVA assumptions of normality, homogeneity of variance, linearity, and homogeneity of regression slopes were tested and met before conducting the ANCOVA. It was also used to analyze significant differences in learners' self-efficacy scores across the four dimensions, using pre-test scores as covariates. All statistical analyses were performed with appropriate software, and all hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 significance level.

RESULTS

Table 1. Level of academic achievement of learners in Science in STLA and non-STLA of pre-test and post-test

	Pre-test				Post-test			
	STLA		non-STLA		STLA		non-STLA	
Raw score	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
65 – 80 (Very High Performance)	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	4	11.11%	0	0.00%
49 – 64 (High Performance)	8	22.22%	4	11.11%	22	61.11%	5	13.89%
33 – 48 (Moderate Performance)	19	52.78%	15	41.67%	10	27.78%	31	86.11%
17 – 32 (Low Performance)	8	22.22%	16	44.44%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
1 – 16 (Very Low Performance)	1	2.78%	1	2.78%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
Total	36	100.00%	36	100.00%	36	100.00%	36	100.00%
MEAN	39.56		35.22		53.78		41.47	

MPS	49.44% (Moderate performance)	44.03% (Moderate performance)	67.22% (High Performance)	51.84% (Moderate performance)
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Legend: 65-80 Very High Performance (VHP), 49-64 High Performance (HP), 33-48 Moderate Performance (MP), 17-32 Low Performance (LP), 1- 16 Very Low Performance (VLP)

Table 2. Learner's self-efficacy in terms of perceived control in STLA and non-STLA

Indicators	STLA				Non-STLA			
	Pre-test		Post-test		Pre-test		Post-test	
	Mean	QI	Mean	QI	Mean	QI	Mean	QI
I will succeed because I can improve my study habits.	3.69	P	4.81	HP	3.14	MP	3.22	MP
Because I develop good study habits, I learn more.	2.47	N	4.53	HP	2.83	MP	3.22	MP
I will be able to finish Junior high school because I am smart enough.	3.33	MP	4.50	P	2.81	MP	3.28	MP
I give the correct answer when I am called in recitations because I paid attention.	3.19	MP	4.50	P	2.67	MP	3.33	MP
I can successfully control the outcome of my performance tasks, such as group presentations, oral works, multimedia presentations, and research projects.	2.72	MP	4.42	P	2.22	N	3.33	MP
I believe that I can pass Science subject because I have the ability to do so.	2.39	N	4.39	P	2.56	MP	3.11	MP
I can successfully control the outcome of written works in my academics, such as quizzes, units, and long tests.	2.33	N	4.39	P	2.28	N	3.50	MO
My teachers see me as a good student.	2.64	MP	4.33	P	2.53	MP	3.14	MP
The future depends on what I do now.	2.53	MP	4.33	P	2.28	N	3.25	MP
My teachers give me high marks because I deserve it.	2.28	N	4.25	P	2.00	N	3.19	MP

Passing a subject depends on how well I perform.	2.94	MP	4.17	P	2.72	MP	3.19	MP
OVERALL MEAN	2.78	MP	4.42	P	2.55	MP	3.25	MP

Legend: 4.51 - 5.00 Highly Positive (HP), .51 – 4.50 Positive (P), 2.51 – 3.50 Moderately Positive (MP), 1.51 – 2.50 Negative (N), 1.00 – 1.50 Highly Negative (HN)

Table 3. Learner's self-efficacy in terms of competence in the STLA and non-STLA

Indicators	STLA				Non-STLA			
	Pre-test		Post-test		Pre-test		Post-test	
	Mean	QI	Mean	QI	Mean	QI	Mean	QI
I can perform my tasks in my academics, such as group presentations, oral work, multimedia presentations, and research projects.	2.36	N	4.67	HP	2.00	N	3.22	MP
I can do an excellent job in my subjects.	2.25	N	4.61	HP	2.08	N	3.28	MP
I can perform very well in any field I get into.	2.56	MP	4.61	HP	2.31	N	3.33	MP
I am competent to pass the Science subject.	2.33	N	4.61	P	1.89	N	3.25	MP
I do things creatively, and it helps me get a good mark.	2.47	N	4.58	HP	2.31	N	3.19	MP
In whatever I do, I strive to attain excellence.	2.33	N	4.47	HP	2.14	N	3.50	MP
I can get good grades in my written works, such as quizzes, unit tests, or long tests.	2.39	N	4.47	P	1.72	N	3.28	MP
During exams, I do not feel anxious because I know I can pass the test with high marks.	2.50	N	4.39	P	2.08	N	3.14	MP
I do not worry about the assigned task for me in class.	2.14	N	4.44	P	2.03	N	3.28	MP
My teachers see me as one of the best students in class.	2.25	N	4.33	P	1.89	N	3.19	MP
I can do my quarterly assessments, such as periodical tests.	2.61	N	4.31	P	2.67	N	3.14	MP
Compared with my classmates, I think that I am a better academic performer.	1.83	N	4.28	P	2.42	N	3.25	MP

On-the-spot recitations do not make me nervous because I can answer them well.	2.19	N	4.17	P	2.11	N	3.33	MP
I am convinced that I can master the concepts and topics taught in my class.	2.28	N	4.06	P	2.36	N	3.25	MP
OVERALL MEAN	2.32	N	4.33	P	2.14	N	3.26	MP

Legend: 4.51 - 5.00 Highly Positive (HP), .51 – 4.50 Positive (P), 2.51 – 3.50 Moderately Positive (MP), 1.51 – 2.50 Negative (N), 1.00 – 1.50 Highly Negative (HN)

Table 4. Learner’s self-efficacy in terms of persistence in the STLA and non-STLA

Indicators	STLA				Non-STLA			
	Pre-test		Post-test		Pre-test		Post-test	
	Mean	QI	Mean	QI	Mean	QI	Mean	QI
If I try really hard, I can get through even the most challenging subject.	2.39	N	4.64	HP	2.06	N	3.28	MP
Despite discouragement from peers, I still continue to study hard.	2.42	N	4.58	HP	2.38	MP	3.31	MP
In spite of the pressures in school, I continue to maintain my good grades.	2.14	N	4.56	HP	2.11	N	3.44	MP
I know how to help myself, and that is by persistently working hard.	2.25	N	4.56	HP	2.00	N	3.28	MP
I consistently figure out how to do the most difficult class work.	2.47	N	4.47	P	2.22	N	3.14	MP
I persistently solve problems with regard to my academic subjects.	2.11	N	4.44	P	2.14	N	3.33	MP
I manage to pull through even when others think there is no hope in passing a subject.	2.42	N	4.36	P	2.00	N	3.36	MP
Regardless of obstacles, I keep moving toward my goal.	2.33	N	4.34	P	2.44	N	3.22	MP

I will not give up; I can figure out difficult homework.	2.61	MP	4.25	P	2.75	MP	3.14	MP
When I'm having a hard time understanding the lesson, I never stop trying.	2.44	N	4.22	P	2.44	N	3.22	MP
If I don't give up, I can do almost all hard tasks in school.	2.14	N	4.19	P	2.11	N	3.19	MP
OVERALL MEAN	2.34	N	4.42	P	2.23	N	3.27	MP

Legend: 4.51 - 5.00 Highly Positive (HP), .51 – 4.50 Positive (P), 2.51 – 3.50 Moderately Positive (MP), 1.51 – 2.50 Negative (N), 1.00 – 1.50 Highly Negative (HN)

Table 5. Learners' self-efficacy in terms of self-regulated learning in STLA and non-STLA

Indicators	STLA				Non-STLA			
	Pre-test		Post-test		Pre-test		Post-test	
	Mean	QI	Mean	QI	Mean	QI	Mean	QI
Even if there are many obstacles, I can learn it.	2.06	N	4.67	HP	1.89	N	3.11	MP
I can submit my requirements before deadlines.	2.25	N	4.58	HP	1.81	N	3.39	MP
Despite obstacles, I am able to accomplish my performance tasks in my academics, such as group presentations, oral work, multimedia presentations, and research projects.	2.36	N	4.50	P	2.08	N	3.28	MP
When I commit mistakes, I am willing to adjust my behavior.	2.08	N	4.50	P	2.78	MP	3.39	MP
I am motivated to excel in my quarterly assessment in my academics, such as periodical exams.	2.25	N	4.47	P	2.39	N	3.14	MP
I can remember the presented discussions in class.	2.14	N	4.44	P	2.14	N	3.19	MP
I can motivate myself to learn.	2.36	N	4.44	P	2.28	N	3.22	MP
I can study on my own.	2.53	MP	4.44	P	2.64	MP	3.61	MP
I can motivate myself to do my schoolwork and assignments.	2.22	N	4.44	P	2.94	MP	3.39	MP
I organize and plan proficiently to succeed in my performance tasks in my academics, such as group presentations, oral work, multimedia presentations, and research projects.	2.14	N	4.44	P	1.72	N	3.19	MP
I arrange my study room to learn without distractions.	2.03	N	4.42	P	2.24	N	3.25	MP
I believe I perform at my best in written works in my academics, such as quizzes, units, or extended tests.	2.28	N	4.42	P	2.08	N	3.19	MP

I can apply my lessons in textbooks.	2.22	N	4.42	P	1.94	N	3.19	MP
I can focus on studying.	2.22	N	4.39	P	2.25	N	3.19	MP
I organize my schoolwork.	2.50	N	4.36	P	2.28	N	3.42	MP
Whenever there are suggestions regarding my negative study habits, I welcome them to change.	2.28	N	4.33	P	2.61	MP	3.42	MP
I work hard despite difficulties to get good grades in written works in my academics, such as quizzes, units, or long tests.	1.94	N	4.31	P	2.11	N	3.14	MP
I can adjust whenever there are hard activities in class.	2.19	N	4.31	P	2.42	N	3.28	MP
I plan my school activities.	2.56	MP	4.25	P	1.89	N	3.25	MP
I can monitor my learning development.	2.31	N	4.19	P	2.25	N	3.33	MP
OVERALL MEAN	2.25	N	4.42	P	2.20	N	3.28	MP

Legend: 4.51 - 5.00 Highly Positive (HP), .51 – 4.50 Positive (P), 2.51 – 3.50 Moderately Positive (MP), 1.51 – 2.50 Negative (N), 1.00 – 1.50 Highly Negative (HN)

Table 6. Summary of Learner’s Self-efficacy Towards Systems Thinking Learning Approach

Indicators	Non-STLA				STLA			
	Pre-test		Post-test		Pre-test		Post-test	
	Mean	QI	Mean	QI	Mean	QI	Mean	QI
1. Perceived control	2.55	MP	3.25	MP	2.78	MP	4.42	P
2. Competence	2.14	MP	3.26	MP	2.32	MP	4.43	P
3. Persistence	2.23	MP	3.27	MP	2.34	MP	4.42	P
4. Self-regulated learning	2.39	MP	3.28	MP	2.25	MP	4.42	P
OVERALL MEAN	2.33	MP	3.27	MP	2.42	MP	4.42	P

Legend: 4.51 - 5.00 Highly Positive (HP), .51 – 4.50 Positive (P), 2.51 – 3.50 Moderately Positive (MP), 1.51 – 2.50 Negative (N), 1.00 – 1.50 Highly Negative (HN)

Table 7. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of learners’ post-test scores

GROUP	N	Mean	SD
Non-Systems Thinking Learning Approach	36	41.47	5.39
Systems Thinking Learning Approach	36	53.78	8.01
Total	72	47.63	9.18

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
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PRE-TESTPRE-TEST	64.070	1	64.070	1.380	.244
GROUP	2782.007	1	2782.007	59.929	<.001
Error	3203.125	69	46.422		
Total	169299.000	72			
Corrected Total	5992.875	71			

Legend: **p<0.05

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
PRETEST_SEF_EFFICACY	.155	1	.155	3.819	.055
GROUP	20.089	1	20.089	494.860	<.001
Error	2.801	69	.041		
Total	1090.892	72			

Legend: **p<0.05

Table 8. Comparison of learners' self-efficacy between classes exposed to non-STLA and STLA groups after adjusting for their pre-test scores.

GROUP	N	Mean	SD
Non-Systems Thinking Learning Approach	36	3.27	.20
Systems Thinking Learning Approach	36	4.42	.21
Total	72	3.84	.61

DISCUSSION

Learners' Academic Achievement in Science

Table 1 shows the level of academic achievement of learners in Science before and after the implementation of the STLA and non-STLA. In the pre-test results, the STLA group recorded a mean score of 39.56 or an MPS of 49.44%, interpreted as average performance. Within this group, one learner (2.78%) showed very low performance, eight learners (22.22%) had low performance, 19 learners (52.78%) achieved moderate performance, and eight learners (22.22%) attained high performance. Similarly, the non-STLA group obtained a mean score of 35.22 or an MPS of 44.03%, also within the

average performance range. In this group, one learner (2.78%) performed very low, 16 learners (44.44%) were low, 15 learners (41.67%) were moderate, and four learners (11.11%) were high performers.

In the post-test, both groups showed improvement, with the STLA group outperforming the non-STLA group. The STLA group achieved a mean score of 53.78 or an MPS of 67.22%, which falls under the above-average performance category. Meanwhile, the non-STLA group obtained a mean score of 41.47 or an MPS of 51.84%, still within the average performance range. Notably, 61.11% of STLA learners scored in the above-average range (61–80%), while 11.11% reached very high performance (81–100%). On the other hand, most non-STLA learners (86.11%) remained within the moderate range (41–60%), with no learners attaining higher performance levels.

Based on the results, learners who were taught under the STLA considerably outperformed the other learners in terms of academic performance. The increase in MPS among STLA learners from 49.44% to 67.22% suggests that this method promoted a deeper comprehension and competence of scientific ideas. The non-STLA group, on the other hand, only slightly increased from 44.03% to 51.84%, suggesting that their academic progress was limited.

The STLA group's improved post-test results show how well the STLA works to help learners make connections between ideas, identify cause-and-effect relationships, and gain a deeper understanding. This teaching method seems to encourage integrative thinking in learners, enabling them to use what they have learned in a variety of scientific contexts.

Integrating STLA into science instruction can result in more effective and long-lasting learning outcomes because it encourages learners to view scientific concepts as interconnected systems rather than individual facts. By fostering analytical thinking, problem-solving, and knowledge transfer, STLA helps learners develop the skills necessary to tackle real-world scientific and environmental issues.

This aligns with the study by Fathurrohman (2023), which shows that most learners scored an average on the pre-test. His research reported that students at Vocational Studies of IPB University achieved a pre-test average score of 61 during his study, "Pre-test and Post-test Technique to Control Students' Mastery in Online Learning of English for Communication Courses at Vocational Studies of IPB University." The findings reveal that learners start instruction with only average levels of understanding, confirming that education significantly helps improve their scores. This is consistent with Blatti et al. (2019) which showed that participants' pretest mean was 48.44% prior to the use of collaborative learning models.

The research findings of this study align with the results reported by Singkirat et al. (2020), who analyzed the effectiveness of the STLA in Grade 11 biology education. Learners who used STLA demonstrated better academic results than those in traditional settings, especially with complex concepts like endocrine system analysis. The results showed that

learners in the STLA group achieved higher academic scores in Science than those in the non-STLA group. The research indicates that teaching learners using the STLA promotes better understanding of interconnected ideas, leading to higher academic achievement.

The results of this study are also supported by Liu (2023), who investigated undergraduate learners' systems thinking skills in climate change education. The study revealed a correlation between learners' levels of systems thinking ability and their acquisition of content knowledge, as those in interdisciplinary courses that focused on systems thinking demonstrated significant improvements in their academic performance. The current research findings confirm these results because learners who received instruction through the STLA achieved better academic outcomes in Science.

Learners' Self-Efficacy in Science

Perceived Control

Table 2 shows the self-efficacy of the learners at the pre-test and post-test of STLA. This aspect is a belief of the learners in their ability to control learning behaviors and shape the academic performance through hard work, discipline and planning. The findings indicate that learners in STLA group scored higher in mean scores in post-test than learners in non-STLA group. The three highest means scores for the STLA group were "I will succeed because I can improve my study habits" (M = 4.81, Highly Positive), "Because I develop good study habits, I learn more" (M = 4.53, Highly Positive) and "I give the correct answer when I am called in recitations because I paid attention" (M = 4.50, Highly Positive).

While non-STLA group had recorded the three highest means scores on "I can effectively manage the product of written work in my academics including quizzes, units and long test" (M= 3.50, Moderately Positive), "I believe that I can pass Science subject because I have the ability to pass in science" (M= 3.11, Moderately Positive), and "I give the correct answer when I am called in recitation because I paid attention" (M= 3.33, Moderately Positive).

The STLA group had the lowest scores in the indicators "I can successfully control the outcome of my written works in academics, including group presentation units, oral work, multimedia presentation, and research project" (M = 4.39, Positive), "I believe I can successfully pass Science subject because I have the ability to pass science subject" (M = 4.39, Positive), and "I can successfully achieve control of the outcome of my performance tasks such as group presentation, oral work, multimedia presentation and research projects" (M = 4.42, Positive).

In the case of non-STLA group, the lowest were "I will succeed because I can improve my study habits" (M = 3.22, Moderately Positive), "Because I develop good study habits, I learn more" (M = 3.22, Moderately Positive) and "I can successfully control the result of

my performance tasks, such as group presentations, oral works, multimedia presentations and research projects” (M = 3.33, Moderately Positive).

The data show that the level of perceived control in the STLA group was higher than that in the non-STLA group. The learners who were exposed to the STLA responded positively with a high level of confidence regarding the issue on their ability to work around their study habits, focus in the classroom and affect the overall academic outcomes with conscious efforts. The reported improvement is indicative of the empowerment characteristics of STLA that encourage self-regulating learning, active learning and metacognition.

Conversely, the non-STLA group had a less than desirable but a mildly positive perceived level of control, indicating an insignificant effect on the increase of self-efficacy. Their answers reflect that they depended on extrinsic conditions instead of taking the responsibility themselves, which means that the conventional instructional approaches were inadequate to create awareness in the learners regarding the consequences of their actions and approaches to learning. The indicators were slightly lower in both groups, particularly the ones associated with controlling the results of written and performance work, which could indicate that learners believed that they could work on their habits and attention more, but were not as confident in their ability to handle more complicated academic works. This could be credited to the greater intellectual exertion of the tasks of Science that involve critical thinking, synthesis and co-working abilities.

It indicates that the perceived control in the STLA group was better compared to the non-STLA group. The group of learners that faced no negative attitudes and harbored high confidence on the issue about their capability of working around their study habits, classroom concentration and overall school performance through conscious efforts is positive. The given improvement is suggestive of the empowerment nature of STLA that promotes self-regulating learning, active learning and metacognition.

The non-STLA group, on the other hand, had a negative yet slightly and non-significantly positive perceived level of control, which implied that there was an insignificant influence of the perceived level of control on the elevation of self-efficacy. What their responses imply is they relied on extrinsic terms rather than deciding themselves which implies that the traditional method of teaching was not sufficient to make the learners aware about the implications of their activities and their way of learning.

The results supported Bandura’s (1997) theory of self-efficacy. This theory suggests that people’s beliefs in their abilities greatly affect their motivation, perseverance, and success. The notable improvement among STLA learners also supports Blatti et al. (2019). They pointed out that many Science learners have difficulty connecting concepts and applying knowledge in real-world situations. Systems-thinking instruction helps close these gaps by promoting a broader understanding.

Similarly, Sweeney et. al (2000) found that teaching based on systems helps learners understand complex cause-and-effect relationships. This approach allows them to gain

more confidence and take control of their learning processes. Together, these findings show that incorporating systems-thinking methods in Science education not only develops cognitive understanding but also boosts learners' self-efficacy and ownership of their learning.

According to Perry et al. (2005), perceived control has a strong predictive power for the academic adjustment of first-year learners, reduces dropout rates, and enhances academic achievement. Recently, the effects mentioned above, such as those on stress and anxiety related to emotional differentiation, including the mediating role of perceived academic control, have also been demonstrated among Chilean university learners (Zapata et al., 2023). Similarly, the study conducted by Stupnisky et al. (2012) found that learners with higher and stable perceived control levels achieved better academic performance and greater flexibility. These findings confirm that non-STLA learners exhibited low baseline control beliefs, and they showed very little improvement during the post-intervention period. In contrast, STLA learners exhibited a significant increase in their control beliefs, demonstrating that the STLA effectively fosters beliefs in agency, effort, and academic control.

Competence

Table 3 shows the learners' self-efficacy in terms of competence in the STLA and non-STLA. The data reveal that learners in the STLA group demonstrated a significant increase in their self-efficacy levels from pre-test to post-test, indicating a more positive outlook on their academic competence after the intervention. The three highest post-test mean scores for the STLA group were: "I can perform my tasks in my academics, such as group presentations, oral work, multimedia presentations, and research projects" (M = 4.67, HP), "I can do an excellent job in my subjects" (M = 4.61, HP), and "I can perform very well in any field I get into" (M = 4.61, HP). These results were qualitatively interpreted as Highly Positive (HP), suggesting that the learners developed strong confidence in their academic competence and abilities across various learning contexts.

On the other hand, the three lowest mean scores for the STLA group were observed in: "I am convinced that I can master the concepts and topics taught in my class" (M = 4.06, P), "On-the-spot recitations do not make me nervous because I can answer them well" (M = 4.17, P), and "During exams, I do not feel anxious because I know I can pass the test with high marks" (M = 4.39, P). Although these scores are slightly lower, they still fall within the Positive (P) range, reflecting consistent self-belief among learners.

For the non-STLA group, the three highest post-test mean scores were found in: "In whatever I do, I strive to attain excellence" (M = 3.50, MP), "I can perform very well in any field I get into" (M = 3.33, MP), and "On-the-spot recitations do not make me nervous because I can answer them well" (M = 3.33, MP). Meanwhile, the three lowest mean scores were obtained in: "I can get good grades in my written works, such as quizzes, unit tests, or long tests" (M = 3.28, MP), "I can perform my tasks in my academics, such as group presentations, oral work, multimedia presentations, and research projects" (M = 3.22, MP), and "I do things creatively, and it helps me get a good mark" (M = 3.19, MP).

All indicators were interpreted as Moderately Positive (MP), indicating that while non-STLA learners maintain some degree of confidence, their perceived competence is comparatively lower than that of the STLA group.

The findings show a distinct difference between the two groups. The STLA successfully increased learners' confidence and competence in completing academic tasks, as evidenced by the STLA group's improvement from Negative (N) or Undecided (U) levels in the pre-test to Highly Positive (HP) levels in the post-test. This implies that the method encouraged in-depth comprehension, engaged engagement, and connected thinking, all of which were crucial components that fostered learners' confidence in their own skills. The non-STLA group, on the other hand, maintained their self-efficacy within the Moderately Positive (MP) range, indicating general motivation and effort rather than mastery of particular academic competencies. Based on the result, traditional teaching approaches might help learners become more persistent, but they won't help them become more confident when tackling challenging, integrative, or performance-based assignments.

These results suggest that applying the STLA helps learners develop a deeper sense of academic competency. STLA helps learners see how their learning contributes to solving larger problems by highlighting the connections between ideas and real-world relevance. This boosts learners' confidence to perform well in a variety of academic settings. In addition to enhancing learners' cognitive abilities, the method increases their emotional fortitude and confidence when completing science assignments.

Conversely, the comparatively lower scores of the Non-STLA group imply that traditional instruction may not be enough to foster deeper self-efficacy and higher-order skills, even though it may be sufficient for basic learning outcomes. This emphasizes how schools must use more systems-oriented and student-centered teaching strategies to boost learners' self-esteem and proficiency.

The results support the findings of Blatti et al. (2019), who claimed that when learning science using conventional methods, many learners find it difficult to make connections between ideas and apply what they have learned to real-world situations. Similarly, Sweeney et al. (2000) discovered that systems-based learning improves confidence and performance by improving understanding of cause-and-effect relationships.

Wolff et al. (2024) stated that learners with low baseline competence beliefs tend to exhibit what is known as self-efficacy inertia, where significant improvement is nearly impossible without specific pedagogical assistance. The learners who did not improve according to the STLA in this study made minimal gains and remained in the moderate positive category despite the intervention. STLA learners showed notable changes in self-efficacy scores, ranging from negative to highly positive levels.

This finding aligns with Puozzo et al. (2021), whose research indicates that educational practices with a structured approach designed to build confidence and creativity have strong potential to enhance perceived competence among learners.

Similarly, Hayat et al. (2020) found that academic self-efficacy not only helps predict better use of metacognitive strategies but also directly improves academic performance. These results support the idea that the STLA effectively develops competence-based self-views, empowering learners to approach academic challenges with greater confidence and strategic effort.

Persistence

Table 4 shows the learners' self-efficacy in terms of persistence under both the STLA and non-STLA. The data indicate a notable improvement among learners exposed to STLA, as reflected in their post-test scores. The three highest post-test mean scores for the STLA group were observed in: "If I try really hard, I can get through even the most challenging subject" (M = 4.64, HP), "Despite discouragement from peers, I still continue to study hard" (M = 4.58, HP), and "In spite of the pressures in school, I continue to maintain my good grades" (M = 4.56, HP). These items were rated as Highly Positive (HP), suggesting that learners developed strong persistence and determination to achieve academic success despite challenges.

Meanwhile, the three lowest post-test mean scores for the STLA group were found in: "If I don't give up, I can do almost all hard tasks in school" (M = 4.19, P), "When I'm having a hard time understanding the lesson, I never stop trying" (M = 4.22, P), and "I will not give up; I can figure out difficult homework" (M = 4.25, P). Although slightly lower, these indicators still fall under the Positive (P) category, showing that the learners maintain a strong, though slightly less intense, level of persistence in more difficult or frustrating learning situations.

For the non-STLA group, the three highest post-test mean scores were found in: "In spite of the pressures in school, I continue to maintain my good grades" (M = 3.44, MP), "Despite discouragement from peers, I still continue to study hard" (M = 3.31, MP), and "I manage to pull through even when others think there is no hope in passing a subject" (M = 3.36, MP). The three lowest mean scores were: "I consistently figure out how to do the most difficult class work" (M = 3.14, MP), "I will not give up; I can figure out difficult homework" (M = 3.14, MP), and "If I don't give up, I can do almost all hard tasks in school" (M = 3.19, MP). All of these were interpreted as Moderately Positive (MP), indicating that non-STLA learners exhibit moderate persistence but with less conviction than those in the STLA group.

The results show that the STLA successfully increased learners' self-efficacy in persevering through academic challenges, as the STLA group exhibits a significant increase in persistence from Negative (N) in the pre-test to Highly Positive (HP) in the post-test. This improvement implies that STLA encourages a deeper comprehension of learning processes and connections, which may help learners approach challenging assignments with confidence and a problem-solving mindset. While the non-STLA group did not exhibit the same level of determination and resilience as the STLA learners, they did maintain a Moderately Positive (MP) level of persistence, indicating a slight improvement over their pre-test scores. Instead of internalized confidence or a growth

mindset fostered by systems-based learning, their perseverance seems to be based on external motivation, such as meeting expectations or maintaining grades.

These results suggest that the STLA is essential for cultivating learners' perseverance, particularly in the face of academic challenges. The STLA enables learners to see connections between concepts, comprehend the wider picture, and view setbacks as chances for growth rather than obstacles. This viewpoint develops persistence, allowing learners to maintain their motivation in the face of stress or discouragement.

The moderate persistence levels of non-STLA learners, on the other hand, imply that conventional teaching methods might not offer enough scaffolding to foster sustained effort in task completion or problem-solving. When faced with difficult science concepts, learners might rely more on routine effort than adaptive persistence. These findings are similar to those of Popescu et al. (2024), who have demonstrated that a structured self-efficacy training course had a significant effect of increasing academic persistence among high school learners, whereby the mean persistence scores rose massively between pre- and post-tests and also at a five-month follow-up.

Additionally, more general summaries of studies by Macklem (2020) conclude that goal-setting and self-regulation, facilitated by motivation, help achieve long-term academic efforts and resilience through targeted interventions. Heikkinen et al. (2024) concluded that highly efficacious belief learners show more effective goal-setting and persistence routines in the course of complex learning activities. These evidence-based effects of interventions can be traced back to the substantial gains that STLA learners have shown, as they manifest the positive impact of the STLA on learning. This approach is designed to develop perseverance-related self-efficacy, enabling learners to tackle challenging schoolwork with confidence.

Self-Regulated Learning

Table 5 shows the learners' self-efficacy in terms of self-regulated learning for both the STLA and non-STLA groups. The data reveal that the STLA group obtained an overall post-test mean of 4.42 (Positive), while the non-STLA group had 3.28 (Moderately Positive). This indicates that learners exposed to STLA developed stronger self-regulated learning skills compared to those who were taught using traditional instruction. The results reflect the learners' ability to plan, monitor, and evaluate their learning independently.

The three highest mean scores for the STLA group were "Even if there are many obstacles, I can learn it" (M = 4.67, Highly Positive), "Despite obstacles, I am able to accomplish my performance tasks in my academics, such as group presentations, oral work, multimedia presentations, and research projects" (M = 4.50, Positive), and "When I commit mistakes, I am willing to adjust my behavior" (M = 4.50, Positive). These indicate that STLA learners have developed resilience, adaptability, and persistence in dealing with academic challenges. The approach encouraged them to reflect on their progress and make necessary adjustments to improve performance.

For the non-STLA group, the three highest indicators were “I can study on my own” (M = 3.61, Moderately Positive), “Despite obstacles, I am able to accomplish my performance tasks...” (M = 3.39, Moderately Positive), and “When I commit mistakes, I am willing to adjust my behavior” (M = 3.39, Moderately Positive). Although they also displayed self-regulation, their development was less profound, suggesting that traditional teaching provided limited opportunities for reflective and independent learning.

The three lowest mean scores for the STLA group were “I work hard despite difficulties to get good grades in written works” (M = 4.31, Positive), “I can adjust whenever there are hard activities in class” (M = 4.31, Positive), and “I plan my school activities” (M = 4.25, Positive). Meanwhile, the non-STLA group’s lowest were “I can focus on studying” (M = 3.19, Moderately Positive), “I organize my schoolwork” (M = 3.19, Moderately Positive), and “I can apply my lessons in textbooks” (M = 3.19, Moderately Positive). The lower means in the non-STLA group show that they were less likely to maintain focus and organization, possibly due to a lack of structured metacognitive support. These results suggest that by enabling learners to take charge of their academic assignments, track their progress, and persevere through challenges, the STLA successfully fosters self-regulated learning. Learners who participated in STLA developed the resilience, reflection, and goal-oriented necessary for lifelong learning. Despite improvements, the non-STLA group showed less consistency in controlling their study habits and staying motivated.

These results agree with Chen et al. (2022) (meta-analysis) findings, which indicate that the SRL interventions have a significant positive effect on the self-efficacy of the learners. On the same note, Follmer (2023) has shown that classroom instruction designed to include SRL activities is highly effective in enhancing planning, motivation, and self-regulation behaviors among students. In addition to it, Simon-Grabalos et al. (2025) present a systematic review of interventions applied to the first-year university learners and emphasize that individualized SRL support is effective not only in the development of planning skills, motivational beliefs, but also in strategic regulation. The STLA intervention has resulted in significant growth in SRL self-efficacy, enabling learners to plan, motivate, manage obstacles, collaborate with colleagues, and monitor their learning, ultimately becoming better and more confident.

Overall, the non-STLA group only saw minor improvements, with their scores remaining in the Moderately Positive range across all four areas. This suggests that traditional teaching methods may not be effective in addressing issues related to self-efficacy. These findings indicate that the STLA significantly boosts learners' self-confidence, especially in seeing themselves as capable learners who can persevere, manage their learning experiences, and handle academic tasks. By enhancing these internal beliefs, STLA is more than just a learning method; it empowers learners to become confident, self-motivated, and independent learners, equipping them for lifelong learning.

Summary of Self-efficacy Towards Systems Thinking Learning Approach

Table 6 presents the summary of learners' self-efficacy towards the STLA compared with the non-STLA group. The indicators measured include perceived control, competence, persistence, and self-regulated learning. The pre-test results revealed that both groups exhibited Moderately Positive (MP) levels of self-efficacy. The non-STLA group obtained an overall mean of 2.33, while the STLA group achieved a slightly higher mean of 2.42. These values indicate that, prior to the intervention, learners in both groups moderately believed in their ability to manage tasks, maintain motivation, and regulate their own learning. After the implementation of the STLA, a significant improvement was observed in the STLA group. Their overall mean score increased from 2.42 (MP) to 4.42 (Positive), demonstrating a significant enhancement in learners' confidence and motivation. Specifically, all four indicators, perceived control (4.42), competence (4.43), persistence (4.42), and self-regulated learning (4.42)—shifted from Moderately Positive to Positive interpretation levels. This indicates that learners under the STLA approach developed greater belief in their abilities to persist through learning challenges, regulate their study behavior, and handle academic responsibilities effectively.

In contrast, the non-STLA group showed only a little improvement, with the overall mean increasing from 2.33 (MP) to 3.27 (MP). Although the scores improved across all indicators, the group remained within the Moderately Positive range. This suggests that traditional instructional methods had limited influence on improving learners' self-efficacy compared to the STLA.

STLA is successful in improving learners' non-cognitive qualities, especially perseverance and self-efficacy, in addition to their cognitive abilities. STLA promotes confidence, independence, and self-regulation in learning by motivating learners to see issues holistically and identify connections between scientific ideas. Additionally, the findings show that learners who are exposed to STLA are more likely to be proactive and maintain their motivation when faced with challenges in the classroom. STLA offers learners a broader understanding of problems, thereby enhancing their comprehension of subject content and developing essential non-cognitive skills, including persistence and self-efficacy. Research from Liu (2023) supports these findings, indicating that learners in the STLA group demonstrated better learning outcomes due to the promotion of content understanding through systems thinking competency. Study findings confirm those presented by Singkirat et al. (2020), showing how learners who studied using systems thinking concepts surpassed the non-STLA group in understanding intricate scientific concepts.

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Learners' Academic Achievement in Science

Table 7 presents the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of learners' academic achievement in the post-test, with the pre-test as the covariate between groups. Learners exposed to STLA had a mean score of 53.78 (SD=8.01), while learners exposed to non-STLA had a mean score of 41.47 (SD=5.39). These results show a higher value than non-STLA, thus a significant difference at the 0.001 level in learners' academic achievement

based on their post-test scores. Analysis of covariance demonstrated that the STLA influenced post-test results significantly because the F-value reached 59.929 and $p < .001$. Learners exposed to the STLA perform better academically than those exposed to non-STLA in post-test scoring after pre-test performance adjustment. The obtained large F-value and a significant effect size verify that the STLA directly affects the learner's academic achievement.

Results from the pre-test showed no significant influence on post-test scores, as evidenced by an F value of 1.380 and a p-value of .244. After considering the learning method, learners' initial academic levels did not significantly impact their final test outcomes. The STLA demonstrates primary responsibility for achieving better performance outcomes because it is the essential component that differentiates results from any potential initial knowledge differences between learners. Using the STLA improves learners' comprehension and proficiency of scientific ideas. By enabling learners to identify relationships between elements, comprehend connections, and use holistic reasoning, the STLA promotes a deeper understanding. As a result, this method encourages critical and analytical thinking in addition to better knowledge retention. The outcomes demonstrate that when it comes to fostering academic success, instructional strategies that prioritize interconnected systems and active engagement perform noticeably better than traditional linear teaching approaches.

The results of this study are consistent with Blatti et al. (2019) who found that integrating STLA into instruction promotes holistic understanding by bridging the gap between subject knowledge and real-world applications. Lovett et al. (2021) provide additional supporting proof, revealing that learners participating in systems-thinking-integrated engineering courses exhibited substantial improvements in their self-efficacy and systems-analysis skills post-instruction. Ho (2021) also found that real-world, systems-oriented learning environments improve self-efficacy and academic performance because learners become more sure of themselves when they use concepts that are connected. Learners that received biology instruction based on STLA performed noticeably better than those who received traditional classroom instruction, especially when it came to complex subjects. (Singkirat et al. 2020).

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Learner's Self-Efficacy between Systems Thinking Learning Approach and Non-Systems Thinking Learning Approach

Table 8 compares the self-efficacy of two learner groups after exposure to STLA and non-STLA. The table shows that learners taught using the STLA scored significantly higher on the post-test than those in the non-STLA group. The ANCOVA results indicate that the instructional approach (STLA vs. non-STLA) has a p-value of $<.001$ ($p < .05$), showing a significant difference in post-test scores between the two. Learners exposed to STLA had a mean score of 4.42 (SD=.21), while learners exposed to non-STLA had a mean score of 3.27 (SD=.20). Since the p-value is less than .05, there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis that states, "there is no significant difference in the post-test scores of learners exposed to the STLA and those who were not."

ANCOVA analysis determined that the STLA group participation produced a notably large F-value of 494.860, which established a very high significance level at $p < .001$ for post-test self-efficacy scores. The very high F-value proves that the STLA actively modifies self-efficacy among learners by establishing a significant and practical effect. The covariate pre-test self-efficacy was not statistically significant (F value = 3.819, $p = .055$), suggesting that learners' prior self-efficacy levels had minimal influence on their post-test outcomes. Instead, the difference in self-efficacy scores can be primarily attributed to the STLA used during the intervention. The self-efficacy perceptions of learners demonstrated substantial changes following their participation in the STLA. The large mean score difference and a high F-value indicate that STLA provided learners with better engaging, integrative, and meaningful learning opportunities, thereby boosting their confidence levels. The STLA aligns with Bandura's (1997) social cognitive theory because mastery experiences with active learning support self-efficacy development.

The data shows how the STLA effectively teaches Science. The STLA improved learners' self-efficacy, supporting essential elements for academic achievement. This research confirmed that STLA is effective in educational environments because it helps learners achieve both intellectual and emotional learning targets. The result of this study supports the research conducted by Lovett et al. (2021), which demonstrates that incorporating systems thinking into engineering courses substantially improved learners' self-efficacy. Learners who engaged in systems thinking activities showed significant improvements in their confidence levels, particularly in their ability to apply systems-related competencies.

Systems thinking education in K–12 settings led to improved learner understanding of environmental issues, according to Curwen et al. (2018) research. Learners also gained higher self-efficacy through their knowledge of systems thinking. The participants in this study achieved better results in analyzing complex problems with proposed solutions, aligning with the positive effects observed in individuals who gained confidence in scientific problem-solving. The findings of this research are similar to those of Ignacio et al. (2024) in their study on Filipino teachers. The researchers demonstrated through their research that teachers who learned through systems thinking-based e-learning modules gained better content knowledge and strengthened their holistic reasoning capabilities. The participants achieved enhanced self-efficacy and better cognitive understanding, supporting the idea that systems thinking develops academic confidence.

Conclusions

The learners exposed to STLA perform better academically than those exposed to the non-STLA. The academic achievement, as measured by the pre-test, showed average results for both groups. After the intervention, the STLA group improved their academic achievement to an Above-Average level. While the non-STLA achieved the same level, It Was Average.

The self-efficacy level of the STLA group towards Science before the intervention was moderately positive, and after the intervention, it remained positive. While the self-efficacy level of the non-STLA group before the intervention was moderately positive and after the

intervention remains moderately positive. The post-test assessment revealed a significant change between the two groups.

Learners exposed to STLA have significantly higher post-test scores than those exposed to non-STLA, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis. Therefore, STLA positively influences learners' academic achievement, resulting in higher scores on their post-test. Learners who were taught using the STLA had significantly higher post-test scores compared to the non-STLA group.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are hereby given:

The Systems Thinking Learning Approach (STLA) is recommended for integration into science teachers' teaching and learning strategies, as it can help learners improve their academic achievement.

School administrators and management can include professional development activities and training sessions focused on the systems thinking learning approach, equipping teachers with the skills and methods needed for effective implementation.

Educators across various subject areas may implement STLA, as it promotes self-efficacy in learners. The rise in confidence and belief in their abilities creates a more effective learning environment, which, in turn, is more empowering and engaging.

Science teachers may incorporate the STLA into their teaching because the results showed a significant difference in the academic performance of the learners. Future researchers might carry out similar studies in different subject areas and grade levels to confirm the effectiveness of the Systems Thinking Learning Approach and examine its broader impact on learners.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers confirm that ethical standards were observed in the study. All respondents were informed about the study and guaranteed their right to leave the study at their convenience with no adverse effects. All the participants were guaranteed anonymity and confidentiality and the procedures were exercised according to Data Privacy Act to guarantee the privacy of personal data. The participants have their well-being, dignity, and rights upheld in the whole course of the research. The author state that there was no conflict of interests in the perception of the given study and the absence of plagiarism because of adequate referencing and original writing. The results of the interpretation were performed in an objective and unbiased manner, and all results were utilized only with academic and research purposes. Lastly, the author reveal that support of artificial intelligence was applied solely during language reworking and formatting, and all the other key ideas, analyzes, and conclusions were produced by the researchers.

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